

USE OF TOURIST FACILITIES BASED ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP.

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Abstract: The article contains a number of proposals and considerations, such as the development of public-private partnerships in increasing tourism potential, the creation of great opportunities for employment for the population, and the expansion of the scope of investment resources directed to the development of the hotel industry.

Keywords: Tourism potential, employment, income, hotel business.

Intensive attraction of tourists to Samarkand region, increasing the flow of tourists, turning tourism into the main source of formation of the regional gross product requires the implementation of a number of important measures for the development of tourism in the region.

In line with the rapid growth of foreign and domestic tourists visiting Samarkand, the number of facilities for their reception and accommodation, that is, the number of hotels and guesthouses, the number of rooms and beds in them, is also rapidly increasing. For example, during 2020-2023, the number of hotels in Samarkand is projected to increase from 180 to 250, or 38.9%, and the number of beds in them from 5,060 to 6,150, or 21.5%. During this period, the number of guesthouses will also increase sharply. The number of tour operators engaged in the reception and accommodation of tourists is also predicted to increase rapidly, reaching 270 in 2023. Their growth rate should be 38.5%. In order to develop the tourism sector in the cities and districts of the Samarkand region, the main focus is on increasing the number of hotels, increasing their capacity, building and commissioning new hotels, equipping them in accordance with modern requirements, and developing innovative technologies.

In the current situation in the tourism sector in Samarkand region, we consider the policy aimed at the rapid development of the hotel business to be the right and rational policy. First, hotel services are of primary importance in the structure of tourism services, and they play a major role in leaving a positive impression of the trip on tourists. Second, during important events (Navruz holiday, festival), at the peak of the season, the problem of free accommodation in hotels arises. Third, the shortage of places negatively affects the competitive environment, and as a result, the price of hotel services in Samarkand in Uzbekistan is generally very high. Often, tourists rightly note that they are much higher than in other countries, for example, in Prague, Amsterdam, Rome. However, the level of service quality in only some hotels meets today's requirements. In accordance with the provisions of the Model Regulation on Hotels, in cases where the requirements for the volume and quality of hotel services are not provided, they are determined by mutual agreement between the service provider, that is, the business entity providing hotel services, and the visiting guest, that is, the customer. Thus, the price of hotel services is determined independently at the initiative of the provider. In such a situation, the only way to control hotel prices and prevent them from becoming too high is to strengthen competition. However, the policy of accelerated development of the hotel industry in Samarkand only partially solves the problem of turning tourism into a leading sector of the regional economy. Based on the results of the study, recognizing the correctness of the policy of expanding the scope of investment resources directed at the development of the hotel industry in Samarkand, we would like to make our own proposals for solving some of the existing problems in the activities of hotels in the future and improving the quality of hotel services. Our proposals in this regard are as follows:

-drastically increase the volume of scientific work devoted to the economic foundations and management system of the hotel business, the study of the subtleties of hotel services, and improve the system of teaching hotel services and management at the university level;

- diversifying hotel services, increasing their types and radically improving their quality; developing the art of cultural interaction with guests among hotel employees;

-continuous modernization and optimization of hotel websites, development of high-tech innovative websites, and implementation of online booking mode;

- increasing the role of hotels in the sale of tourism products as an important component of the tourism economy, and rapidly developing a wide range of services for guests, including not only accommodation and catering services, but also transportation, communications, entertainment, excursion services, medicine, sports, beauty salons, and art;

-expanding the hotel network by restoring buildings of historical and artistic value, architectural monuments, palaces, and attracting historical objects that can be converted into hotels. This is because giving tourists the opportunity to live in historical buildings will provide them with additional enjoyment and stimulation.

Realizing the historical and cultural potential of the Samarkand region requires significant investment in the preservation of historical monuments, works of art, manuscripts and museum collections, as well as traditional forms of expression such as music, dance and language. In particular, the preservation of ancient monuments, their preservation for future generations, the prevention and protection of possible future damage by partially preserving the fragments of historical structures that are being destroyed, can be achieved at very high financial costs.

In our opinion, as an important direction for preserving and further enhancing the historical and cultural tourism potential of the Samarkand region, a large amount of work should be carried out on the basis of the principles of public-private partnership. The main work in this direction should be aimed, firstly, at the restoration, conservation and protection of historical monuments, and secondly, at the improvement of the territory of the object and its surroundings, making it attractive and attractive.

In a broad sense, this partnership can be interpreted as a legal mechanism for coordinating the interests of the state and the private sector and ensuring their interdependence. It is an effective means of combining the capabilities of state bodies and business on the basis of establishing mutual cooperation in carrying out tasks important from the point of view of social development.

List of used literature

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